

Original Research

Decoupling Economic Growth and Carbon Footprint: An Empirical Analysis of Ghana's Export Sector, Manufacturing, and Renewable Energy Adoption

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Abstract

The prospect of decoupling economic development from CO₂ emissions in Ghana is examined in this paper, with an emphasis on the manufacturing, export, and adoption of renewable energy sectors. The paper investigates the long-term and short-term correlations among CO₂ emissions, renewable energy consumption (RNE), population growth (POP), manufacturing value-added (MVA), Economic growth (GDP), and exports (EXP) using an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing method using time series data from 1990 to 2020. The outcomes show that the variables are long-term cointegrating. Long-term GDP and CO₂ emissions show a positive but negligible correlation, whereas exports show a negative and insignificant correlation. In the near term, using renewable energy has a markedly undesirable consequence on releases, yet, over time, the connection is positive and negligible. Because the turning point when economic expansion results in lower emissions is not apparent, the Environmental Kuznets Curve concept is not entirely substantiated. The report emphasizes how specific laws encouraging the use of renewable energy, environmentally friendly export and manufacturing processes, and technical advancements are necessary to help Ghana move toward a low-carbon economy.

Keywords: CO₂ emissions, Economic growth, Environmental Kuznets Curve, Granger causality, Ghana.

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Introduction

Being among the most significant worldwide problems of our day, climate change needs immediate attention to reduce its detrimental effects. Nowadays, nations everywhere want to cut their CO₂ footprint and greenhouse gas emissions while reaching viable economic growth (Acheampong et al., 2019). The seriousness of this issue is demonstrated by the fact that global CO₂ emissions hit a record high of 36.8 billion tons in 2022 (International Energy Agency [IEA], 2022). Decoupling economic growth from environmental degradation has gained significant attention, particularly in developing countries striving to balance economic evolution and ecological sustainability (Oteng-Abayie et al., 2022; Nyasapoh et al., 2022). Ghana, a rapidly developing country in West Africa, has experienced substantial economic growth in recent years, driven primarily by its export sector and manufacturing industries. Ghana's GDP grew by 5.4% in 2021 and is projected to grow by 5.5% in 2024 (World Bank, 2022). Nevertheless, this evolution has become a burden to the environment, with increasing CO₂ emissions and environmental degradation (Adeleye et al., 2021; Nyasapoh et al., 2022). According to the study by Friedlingstein et al. (2022), Ghana's CO₂ emissions climbed from 14.3 million tonnes in 2010 to 18.6 million tonnes in 2020, representing a 30% rise in just a decade. As a participant in the Paris Agreement and other international climate accords, Ghana has devoted itself to dropping its greenhouse gas emissions and stimulating ecological development (Prempeh, 2023). The export sector, particularly in natural resource-based economies like Ghana, has been identified as a noteworthy provider of CO₂ emissions and ecological dilapidation (Acheampong et al., 2019; Baajike et al., 2024). The mining and processing of natural capital and the transportation and logistics involved in exporting these commodities have a substantial environmental impact (Mensah et al., 2019). Consequently, decoupling economic growth from environmental degradation in the export sector is crucial for achieving sustainable development goals. Furthermore, the manufacturing sector, which plays a vital role in Ghana's economic growth, is also a significant source of CO₂ emissions and ecological pollution (Oteng-Abayie et al., 2022; Adeleye et al., 2021). Adopting cleaner production technologies, energy-efficient processes, and RNE bases in the manufacturing sector could reduce carbon footprint while sustaining economic growth (Nyasapoh et al., 2022). RNE adoption has emerged as a promising elucidation for decoupling economic growth from carbon emissions (Prempeh, 2023; Nyasapoh et al., 2022). By transitioning to RNE sources, like solar, wind, and hydropower, Ghana can lessen its dependence on fossil fuels and mitigate the environmental impact of its economic activities (Acheampong et al., 2019). However, Ghana's adoption of RNE technologies has been comparatively gradual; in 2020, renewable sources comprised just 1.2% of the nation's overall energy mix. This emphasizes the necessity of policies and incentives to hasten the transition (Energy Commission of Ghana, 2021; Nyasapoh et al., 2022). To address these challenges, empirical analysis is necessary to understand the relationship between GDP, carbon footprint, and the potential drivers of decoupling, such as RNE adoption and sustainable practices in the export and manufacturing sectors (Baajike et al., 2024). When these factors are examined, policymakers and stakeholders can develop effective strategies to promote sustainable economic growth while mitigating the environmental impact of Ghana's economic activities (Oteng-Abayie et al., 2022; Adeleye et al., 2021).

Present papers have generally engrossed on the overall bearing of commercial activity on Ghana's atmosphere without exploring the potential for decoupling economic evolution from CO₂ emissions in essential areas like exports, manufacturing, and renewable energy uptake. An empirical analysis investigating this decoupling potential within these crucial economic drivers is lacking. Addressing climate change while sustaining economic development is a pressing need for Ghana. This study intends to offer a significant understanding of decoupling techniques by examining the roles of the export sector, manufacturing industry, and RNE in reducing CO₂ emissions. The findings can inform policies promoting sustainable economic growth while reducing environmental impact. This study offers empirical evidence on the link between GDP, carbon footprint, and decoupling drivers like sustainable export practices, cleaner manufacturing technologies, and renewable energy adoption. It identifies significant carbon emission sources, enabling targeted interventions. Moreover, it evaluates existing sustainability policies, highlighting areas for improvement and new policy development. Crucially, the study offers recommendations for policymakers to facilitate decoupling economic growth from carbon emissions across the export sector, manufacturing, and through increased renewable energy use. This research contributes to Ghana's efforts towards sustainable development and a low-carbon economy, informing strategies applicable to other developing nations facing similar challenges.

Literature Review

The information from earlier literary works on the correlation among CO₂ emissions, GDP, population growth (POP), manufacturing activities (MVA), and exports (EXP) are included in this part of the study.

Empirical Literature

Several recent studies have examined how different factors, like trade, energy use, and GDP, affect CO₂ emissions in various states. One study by Khan et al. (2020) examined how imports, exports, and GDP impacted CO₂ emissions in nine oil-exporting countries. They found that in the long run, exports hurt CO₂ emissions, while imports and GDP had a positive effect. This means that more exports led to lower CO₂ emissions, but more imports and higher GDP led to higher CO₂ emissions. Aghasafari et al. (2021) showed a two-way link between CO₂ emissions and EXP and a one-way correlation between CO₂ emissions and foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows. They also found that fossil fuel energy use was the core influencer of CO₂ emissions and that being a member of the World Trade Organization (WTO) increased exports and FDI inflows. Iqbal et al. (2022) examined the BRICS economies (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa). They found that in the long run, CO₂ emissions, RNE, EXP, FDI, and savings all positively affected GDP, while interest rates and trade openness had a negative effect. This suggests that as carbon emissions and FDI increased, so did GDP, CO₂ emissions, and FDI in these states. Mahmood (2022) studied spatial analyses of consumption-based CO₂ emissions, exports, imports, and FDI nexus in GCC countries. The study aimed to investigate the direct and spillover effects of Trade and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) on territory-based CO₂ (TCO₂) and consumption-based CO₂ emissions. The author used data from the years 1990 to 2019. The study further employed the Spatial Durbin Model (SDM). The empirical findings confirmed the presence of the environmental Kuznets curve (EKC) in

the relationship between economic growth and emissions in both TCO₂ and CCO₂ models. As a result, economic growth has a positive association with CO₂ emissions during the first phase of the EKC but a negative link with CO₂ emissions later in the EKC. Additionally, the author found that exports have a favorable direct effect on TCO₂ emissions. However, it has negative spillover and direct and total effects on CCO₂ emissions. The researcher further revealed that imports have favorable spillover and direct effects on CO₂ and positive spillover effects on CCO₂ emissions. Also, FDI was seen to have adverse direct and spillover effects on CCO₂ and positive spillover effects on TCO₂. In Latin American countries, Galvan et al. (2022) carried out research to examine the long-term relationship between economic growth, trade, foreign direct investment (FDI), and gross domestic product (GDP) on CO₂ emissions. They used annual time series data for 20 years, from 2000 to 2020. The study's primary purpose was to examine the role of sector value addition to GDP on the CO₂ emission nexus in middle-income economies. The researchers controlled for the effects on GDP, FDI, and Trade. The study employed regression and path analysis (Multiple regression). They also employed the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. The researchers found that for higher-income economies, FDI, GDP, and Trade are significant factors that have a solid favorable impact on CO₂ emission; however, that favorable impact is less in the middle-income trap (MIT) countries. Additionally, the research revealed that FDI, GDP growth, and trade variables could impact environmental quality through CO₂ emission. However, factors such as tourism/travel services and education do not significantly affect environmental quality by CO₂.

Sulaiman and Abdul-Rahim (2018) studied the link between POP and CO₂ emissions in Nigeria over dissimilar periods (1971-2000, 1971-2005, and 1971-2010). They establish that in the long run, POP had little effect on CO₂ emissions during these periods. However, economic development was the main factor driving long-term CO₂ emissions. In the short term, CO₂ emissions were significantly influenced by factors like population growth, economic growth, and energy use. Dong et al. (2018) examined the relationship between CO₂ emissions, GDP, POP, and RNE across 128 states from 1990 to 2014. They showed that, globally and regionally, GDP and POP had a constructive and noteworthy impact on CO₂ emission levels. Chen et al. (2022) found that population growth and urbanization were insignificant drivers of CO₂ emissions. Rehman and Rehman (2022) researched the five most populated regions of Asia (China, India, Indonesia, Pakistan, and Bangladesh) by investigating the impact of urbanization, population growth, Gross domestic product (GDP) per capita, and energy use on CO₂ emissions on environmental degradation in these countries. The authors employed the Grey Relational Analysis (GRA) based on weights and ranking. They collected 14 years of data, starting from 2001 to 2014. The researchers employed the Conservative minimax approach to determine which countries add the most CO₂ emissions based on weights acquired by Second Grey Relational Analysis (SSGRA). Again, the Grey technique for order of preference by similarity to ideal solution (G-TOPSIS) technique was employed for further optimization by prioritizing the explanatory factors that significantly influence CO₂ emissions. The study showed that India contributes to carbon emissions caused by population growth and economic development. China and Pakistan's grounded carbon emission variables are energy use and urbanization. In addition, the G-TOPSIS revealed a direct causative association between unsustainable population increase and CO₂ emissions. Wang et al. (2022) conducted a study in 36 OECD economies to examine the impact of population

aging on economic growth and carbon emissions nexus and the relationship between energy use and carbon emissions. They used the panel threshold regression model to analyze data from 1996 to 2016. Some variables in their study included per capita carbon emissions, economic development (per capita GDP), per capita energy use, and population aging. Also, the control variables were the population size, technological innovation level, the degree of urbanization, industrial structure, and energy intensity. The results showed a population aging threshold effect between per capita GDP and per capita carbon emissions and between per capita energy use and per capita carbon emissions. This indicates that population aging contributes to the decoupling of economic growth and carbon emissions and the decoupling of energy consumption and carbon emissions.

Salari et al. (2021) studied the connection between GDP growth, RNE, and CO₂ emissions in the United States from 1997 to 2016 at the state level. The GDP and CO₂ emissions association followed an inverted U-shape pattern. Cai et al. (2018) used a new bootstrap method to scrutinize the connection between RNE, GDP, and CO₂ emissions in G7 countries. They found no relationship between these factors for the US, UK, France, or Italy. However, there was a link between Japan and Germany when CO₂ emissions were reliant on variables and real GDP per capita was the independent variable. Aslam et al. (2021) examined the relationship between industrialization, economic growth, CO₂ emission, trade openness, and population density in the Chinese economy. The researchers used the environmental Kuznets curve (EKC). The study results showed that population density, industry, and trade increase Chinese CO₂ emissions, while per capita GDP deteriorates CO₂ emissions in the long run. Additionally, they discovered a unidirectional relationship between trade openness structure and population density and a bidirectional causal link between CO₂ emission and industrialization. Variance decomposition impulse analysis highlights the time lag of CO₂ emission, industrialization, and per capita GDP, respectively, significant predictors of Chinese CO₂ emission.

Yang et al. (2021) made the following key findings: (1) Growth in the manufacturing sector significantly increased CO₂ emissions, but this result weakened as the share RNE increased; (2) The relationship between MVA and emissions changed in almost partial of the sample nations and two-thirds of the subsectors; and (3) The manufacturing subsector that primarily relies on natural gas, electricity, and heat grew slower than the subsector using coal, coke, and crude oil. Abokyi et al. (2021) used different methods to investigate the link between electricity consumption and CO₂ emissions in Ghana from 1971 to 2014 in the context of the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis. They analyzed the necessary and sufficient conditions and found a U-shaped relationship, indicating that the EKC hypothesis did not hold for Ghana's MVA during the historical study. Qayyum et al. (2021) examined the affiliation between financial change, RNE, technological advancements, and CO₂ emissions in India from 1980 to 2019, considering economic development and urbanization roles. They concluded that increased use of renewable energy and technological innovations negatively affected CO₂ emissions in the short and long run, suggesting that promoting these measures would lower emissions. Anwar (2022) found that while RNE reduces CO₂ emissions, urbanization, financial development, and GDP increase CO₂ emissions.

Materials and Methods

Theoretical framework and empirical model

The Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis has remained a significant theory in environmental economics, continuing to generate academic discussions and empirical research (Destek & Sarkodie, 2019). The EKC, proposed in the 1990s by economists such as Gene Grossman and Alan Krueger, suggests an inverted U-shaped relationship between environmental degradation and economic growth (Grossman & Krueger, 1995). According to this theory, early economic development is characterized by increased environmental damage due to industrialization and rapid economic expansion. However, when economies reach a certain income per capita threshold, things start to change, and things like stricter environmental regulations, cleaner technology adoption, and raised environmental awareness cause environmental quality to start improving (Sarkodie & Strezov, 2019; Aşıcı & Acar, 2018). While some recent studies have provided empirical evidence supporting the inverted U-shaped curve in various contexts (Destek & Sarkodie, 2019), critics have raised concerns about the generalizability and underlying assumptions of the EKC theory. They argue that the turning point at which environmental quality improves may occur at different income levels across countries and pollutants, depending on economic structure, policy environment, and technological capabilities (Sarkodie & Strezov, 2019; Zhao et al., 2023). Additionally, some studies have suggested that the EKC hypothesis may not hold for certain types of pollution, such as greenhouse gas emissions, which have global impacts and require coordinated international efforts (Erdogan et al., 2020; Ganda, 2019). The relevance of the EKC theory to the study on decoupling economic growth and carbon footprint in Ghana is significant. As a rapidly developing country with a growing export sector and manufacturing industry, Ghana finds itself at a critical juncture where economic growth and environmental sustainability must be carefully balanced. The EKC hypothesis provides a theoretical framework to examine whether Ghana can reach a turning point where economic growth can be achieved while simultaneously reducing carbon emissions and environmental impact (Destek & Sarkodie, 2019). When the relationship between economic growth, carbon footprint, and the potential drivers of decoupling, such as sustainable practices in the export sector, cleaner production technologies in manufacturing, and renewable energy adoption, are analyzed, this study can contribute to the ongoing discourse on the EKC theory and its applicability in Ghana's specific context. The findings may provide insights into the potential turning points or inflection points where economic growth and environmental quality can be decoupled, informing policy decisions and sustainable development strategies. This study explores the possibility of separating economic growth from carbon emissions in Ghana, focusing on the export sector, manufacturing industry, and adopting renewable energy sources. The Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis offers a theoretical basis for examining the relationship between economic growth and environmental degradation. According to the EKC hypothesis, there is an inverted U-shaped link between economic growth and environmental degradation. Initially, environmental degradation increases as the economy grows, but after reaching a certain income level or turning point, it starts to decline. This implies that economic growth leads to more environmental damage at lower income levels. However, as income rises beyond a certain threshold, further economic growth can lead to environmental improvements. This turning point is influenced by

increased environmental awareness, the adoption of cleaner technologies, and the implementation of stringent environmental regulations. In the context of this study, the EKC hypothesis can be applied to analyze whether Ghana can reach a turning point where economic growth, driven by the export sector and manufacturing activities, can be achieved while simultaneously reducing carbon emissions and environmental impact through the adoption of sustainable practices, cleaner production technologies, and increased renewable energy consumption. Based on the theoretical framework and the literature review, the empirical model for the study can be expressed as follows:

$$CO2_t = f(EXP_t, POP_t, GDP_t, MVA_t, RNE_t) \dots (1)$$

Where, EXP_t , POP_t , GDP_t , MVA_t , RNE_t , and $CO2_t$ are Exports (goods and services) EXP, Population growth (POP), Economic growth (GDP per capita), Manufacturing activities (MVA), Renewable energy consumption (RNE), and CO_2 emissions at the time t . A natural logarithmic transformation was applied to all parameters to induce normality in data distribution and mitigate potential issues arising from skewness. Additionally, log-linear specifications were used since they have been shown through empirical research to provide trustworthy data regarding the dynamics of economic growth regarding both independent and dependent variables. The following statement is a theoretical model that outlines the empirical definition of the economic growth function.

$$\ln CO2_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln EXP_t + \beta_2 \ln POP_t + \beta_3 GDP_t + \beta_4 MVA_t + \beta_5 RNE_t + \varepsilon_t \dots (2)$$

Data

The paper used time series data from 1990 to 2020. The World Bank indicator database included the time series data for Exports (goods and services), EXP, Population growth (POP), Economic growth (GDP per capita), Manufacturing activities (MVA), Renewable energy consumption (RNE), and CO_2 emissions. This particular timeframe was selected owing to the obtainability of consistent data across the essential constructs for Ghana. Table 1 includes material on the unit of dimension and data foundation for the chosen variables.

Table 1. Variable Description

Variable	Symbol	Details of Variables	Source
Carbon emissions	CO_2	CO_2 (metric tons per capita)	WDI
Economic Growth	GDP	Per Capita (constant 2015 US\$)	WDI
Manufacturing activities	MVA	Value added (% of GDP)	WDI
Renewable energy consumption	RNE	(% of total final energy consumption)	WDI
Population Growth	POP	Population growth (annual %)	WDI
Exports	EXP	Exports of goods and services (% of GDP)	WDI

Trend graph of variables under consideration

Throughout Time, the graphs show the patterns of many economic, demographic, and environmental factors. Exports (LNEXP), manufacturing activity (LNMVA), population growth (LNPOP), GDP, and CO₂ emissions are the constructs depicted. An overall rising pattern on the export trend line indicates that the export of goods and services increased during the period under consideration. Conversely, population increase seems to be either steady or reducing, suggesting a steady or declining population increase. GDP per capita indicates that economic growth increases with time because of its upward trend. Comparably, the trajectory of manufacturing activity shows an overall rising pattern, indicating that manufacturing activities increased throughout the time under review. The use of RNE sources is trending upward, as shown by the trend line for that energy source. Still, it seems like CO₂ emissions are also rising, which might impact the environment and counteract the advantages of using more renewable energy.

Figure 1. Trend Graphs

Econometrics approach

The study employed the ARDL bounds approach to cointegration to examine the long-term relationship among the variables introduced by Pesaran et al. (2001). Compared to traditional methods, this cointegration test offers several advantages regarding the order of integration (Raihan et al., 2023; Voumik et al., 2023). This approach is applicable when the variables are stationary at either the integrated order of 1 or 0. The ARDL estimation

utilizes an optimal lag structure and operates within a general-to-specific modeling framework to accurately represent the data generation process. The ARDL modeling framework uses the ARDL F-statistic to determine if cointegration exists between the variables (Raihan & Tuspekova, 2022). This is achieved using the most suitable lag length, ensuring a thorough investigation. The F-statistics optimal lag length (l) was determined using the analysis's Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), with the lowest AIC scores indicating the lag length. If the estimated ARDL F-statistic exceeds a predefined upper critical bound, the variables below deliberation are cointegrated. If the F-statistic is below the lower critical threshold, it implies the absence of cointegration between the variables. According to Raihan et al. (2023), the empirical conclusions are unconvincing when the F-statistic falls within the upper and lower critical bounds. The following equation (3) provides a general structure for the ARDL bounds analysis used to find cointegration.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta \ln CO2_t &= \alpha_{01} + \ln CO2_{t-1} \\
 &= +\beta_1 \ln EXP_{t-1} + \beta_2 \ln POP_{t-1} + \beta_3 GDP_{t-1} + \beta_4 MVA_{t-1} + \beta_5 RNE_{t-1} \\
 &+ \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_{1i} \Delta \ln CO2_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^w \alpha_{2i} \Delta \ln EXP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^w \alpha_{3i} \Delta \ln POP_{t-i} \\
 &+ \sum_{i=0}^w \alpha_{4i} \Delta \ln GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^w \alpha_{5i} \Delta \ln MVA_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^w \alpha_{6i} \Delta \ln RNE_{t-i} \\
 &+ \varepsilon_{1t} \quad (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

Δ denotes the first difference operator, and Q is the optimal lag length. After confirming the cointegration between the variables, the study estimated the long-run and short-run effects by applying the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach. Equation (3) was normalized to derive the long-run effects of the components. However, the error correction model (ECM) could be developed by incorporating it into the ARDL technique. According to Voumik et al. (2023), this method provides reliable empirical findings even with small sample sizes. The ECM successfully combines current dynamics with long-run equilibrium to maintain an overall view over an extended time horizon (Raihan, 2023). Due to the existence of these cointegrating vectors, the empirical model can identify and distinguish multiple of them. The symbol represents the coefficient of the ECM θ . The standard range for the value of the ECM coefficient is 0 to 1. To achieve equilibrium, it is crucial to simplify the variance correction process when the ECM yields results that are not statistically significant. In this study, equation (4) was utilized to compute the short-run coefficients of the variables.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta \ln CO2_t &= \alpha_0 + \ln CO2_{t-1} \\
 &= +\beta_1 \ln EXP_{t-1} + \beta_2 \ln POP_{t-1} + \beta_3 GDP_{t-1} + \beta_4 MVA_{t-1} + \beta_5 RNE_{t-1} \\
 &+ \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_{1i} \Delta \ln CO2_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^w \alpha_{2i} \Delta \ln EXP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^w \alpha_{3i} \Delta \ln POP_{t-i} \\
 &+ \sum_{i=0}^w \alpha_{4i} \Delta \ln GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^w \alpha_{5i} \Delta \ln MVA_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^w \alpha_{6i} \Delta \ln RNE_{t-i} \\
 &+ \theta_1 ECT_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{1t} \dots \dots \dots (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

Pairwise Granger causality test

The research sought causal links between the variables using paired Granger causality tests (Granger, 1969). In statistical terms, Granger causality establishes whether the values of one variable in the past can be used to predict the values of another in the future. This method was chosen because, based on previous studies in the field (Islam et al., 2020; Raihan et al., 2023; Raihan & Tuspekova, 2022), it offers some benefits over other time-series data evaluation techniques. The Granger causality test determines whether past values of one variable may be usefully used to forecast future values of another. If adding Y's prior values improves variable X's predictions, then variable X is "Granger-cause" variable Y. F-tests are used to verify Granger causality between the variables X and Y after estimating the coefficients using ordinary least squares (OLS) regression. The variables X_t and Y_t , in turn, represent the values of X and Y at time t. A bivariate autoregressive model accounting for two variables and their lagged values may write the variables X_t and Y_t as follows:

$$X_t = \beta_1 + \sum_{i=1}^w \alpha_i Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^w \mu_i X_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad \dots \dots (5)$$

$$Y_t = \beta_2 + \sum_{i=1}^w \Omega_i Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^w \infty_i X_{t-i} + \mu_t \quad \dots \dots (5)$$

The value of "n" represents the lag length, whereas the parameters $\beta_2, \beta_1, \alpha_i, \Omega_i, \mu_i$, and ∞_i are employed for estimation purposes. Furthermore, the terms ε_t and μ_t denote the stochastic error terms or residuals.

Results and discussion

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics and a correlation matrix for CO₂ emissions, economic indicators, and energy consumption variables. The data spans 31 years, from 1990 to 2020. The means and standard deviations revealed variable variability, with GDP having the highest standard deviation. Furthermore, some variables exhibited skewness and kurtosis, indicating departures from normality. The correlation matrix highlighted several notable relationships. Firstly, CO₂ emissions (LNCO2) have a strong positive correlation with GDP (LNGDP) of 0.948, suggesting that economic growth is associated with higher emissions. On the other hand, CO₂ emissions have a strong negative correlation of -0.966 with renewable energy consumption (LNRNE), implying that increased renewable energy usage corresponds to lower emissions. Moreover, GDP exhibited a strong negative correlation of -0.982 with renewable energy consumption. Additionally, population (LNPOP) displayed moderate negative correlations with CO₂ emissions (-0.373) and GDP (-0.538), indicating that population growth is linked to lower emissions and economic output. However, manufacturing value added (LNMVA) has relatively weaker correlations with the other variables.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics and correlation matrix

Descriptives	YEAR	LNCO2	LNEXP	LNPOP	LNGDP	LNMAVA	LNRNE
Mean	2005	-1.164617	3.407762	0.893952	7.117633	2.195574	4.092244
Median	2005	-1.135373	3.468181	0.897078	7.038947	2.202951	4.117898
Maximum	2020	-0.506025	3.887777	1.011012	7.591667	2.450017	4.417997
Minimum	1990	-1.948632	2.826005	0.725744	6.748081	1.733528	3.69511
Std. Dev.		0.432819	0.278001	0.073187	0.278455	0.167737	0.242482
Skewness		-0.252161	-0.560772	-0.613537	0.385268	-1.071995	0.101622
Kurtosis		1.875658	2.755695	2.942658	1.67428	3.937481	1.540307
Jarque-Bera		1.961376	1.701828	1.949123	3.037042	7.072602	2.805515
Probability		0.375053	0.427024	0.377358	0.219036	0.029121	0.245918
Observations	31	31	31	31	31	31	31
Correlation matrix							
	LNCO2	LNEXP	LNGDP	LNMAVA	LNPOP	LNRNE	
LNCO2	1	0.477755106	0.948176896	0.064274636	-0.37278851	-0.96582973	
LNEXP	0.47775511	1	0.331245796	-0.177454332	-0.00420766	-0.34215503	
LNGDP	0.9481769	0.331245796	1	0.14152174	0.53803662	0.981547471	
LNMAVA	0.06427464	0.177454332	0.14152174	1	0.32553577	0.0692577	
LNPOP	0.37278851	0.004207656	0.53803662	0.325535767	1	0.412839304	
LNRNE	0.96582973	0.342155039	0.98154747	0.0692577	0.412839304	1	

Stationarity check

The study employed the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root tests to assess the stationarity of the variables. These tests examine the null hypothesis, which suggests that the variable contains a unit root, implying non-stationarity. The results of the ADF test indicate that LNCO2, LNEXP, LNGDP, LNMAVA, LNPOP, and LNRNE are non-stationary at the level form when considering both constant and constant and trend criteria. However, after taking the first difference, all variables (d(LNCO2), d(LNEXP), d(LNGDP), d(LNMAVA), d(LNPOP), and d(LNRNE)) become stationary at the 1% or 5% significance level with the constant and constant & trend specifications. The PP test results confirm the findings of the ADF test. Most variables are non-stationary at the level form with the constant and constant trend specifications, except for LNRNE, which is stationary with the constant and trend specification at the 5% level. After taking the first difference, all variables become stationary at the 1% or 5% significance level with the constant, constant, and trend, and no constant and trend specifications. Based on these results, it can be concluded that all variables are integrated of order one, I(1), meaning they become stationary after taking the first difference. This satisfies the condition for proceeding with cointegration analysis, as recommended by Raihan and Tuspekova (2022b, 2022c) and Raihan (2023c, 2023d), to avoid the I(2) series, which can lead to spurious conclusions.

Table 3. Unit root test

Unit Root Test Results Table (Adf)							
At Level							
		LNCO2	LNEXP	LNGDP	LNMAVA	LNPOP	LNRNE
With Constant	t-Statistic	-1.4737	-2.5238	0.0491	-2.3849	-0.7086	0.7127
	Prob.	0.5286	0.1201	0.9558	0.1542	0.8275	0.9903
		n0	n0	n0	n0	n0	n0
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-4.6533	-2.2318	-2.9028	-2.3833	-1.3077	-2.6141
	Prob.	0.0057	0.456	0.1789	0.3801	0.8633	0.2774
		***	n0	n0	n0	n0	n0
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-3.68	0.4606	2.2305	-0.0203	-0.4594	-4.6106
	Prob.	0.0007	0.8081	0.9922	0.668	0.5062	0
		***	n0	n0	n0	n0	***
At First Difference							
		d(LNCO2)	d(LNEXP)	d(LNGDP)	d(LNMAVA)	d(LNPOP)	d(LNRNE)
With Constant	t-Statistic	-6.707	-5.6722	-3.0729	-6.24	-2.0978	-5.8055
	Prob.	0	0.0001	0.04	0	0.247	0
		***	***	**	***	n0	***
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-3.6385	-5.8074	-3.0073	-6.199	-3.224	-5.8921
	Prob.	0.0484	0.0003	0.1474	0.0001	0.1017	0.0002
		**	***	n0	***	n0	***
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-2.1148	-5.6782	-2.0027	-6.347	-2.0993	-0.2526
	Prob.	0.0353	0	0.0449	0	0.0366	0.5854
		**	***	**	***	**	n0
Unit Root Test Results Table (Pp)							
At Level							
		LNEXP	LNCO2	LNGDP	LNMAVA	LNPOP	LNRNE
With Constant	t-Statistic	-2.4938	-0.1908	0.8643	-2.3851	-0.4284	0.8613
	Prob.	0.1269	0.9294	0.9935	0.1542	0.8917	0.9935
		n0	n0	n0	n0	n0	n0
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-2.159	-3.5127	-1.7067	-2.3738	-0.7497	-3.9991
	Prob.	0.4939	0.0561	0.7232	0.3847	0.9594	0.0198
		n0	*	n0	n0	n0	**
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	0.5001	-4.6815	6.4424	0.0305	-1.1599	-4.7281
	Prob.	0.8176	0	1	0.6847	0.2188	0
		n0	***	n0	n0	n0	***
At First Difference							
		d(LNEXP)	d(LNCO2)	d(LNGDP)	d(LNMAVA)	d(LNPOP)	d(LNRNE)
With Constant	t-Statistic	-5.6722	-9.4838	-3.0542	-6.2669	-2.3056	-9.2403
	Prob.	0.0001	0	0.0416	0	0.177	0
		***	***	**	***	n0	***
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-5.8129	-15.1638	-2.7808	-6.2407	-2.1855	-9.3184

Unit Root Test Results Table (Adf)							
	Prob.	0.0003	0	0.2149	0.0001	0.4794	0
		***	***	n0	***	n0	***
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-5.6788	-5.179	-1.9641	-6.3746	-2.2417	-5.785
	Prob.	0	0	0.0488	0	0.0264	0
		***	***	**	***	**	***

a: (*) Significant at the 10%; (**) Significant at the 5%; (***) Significant at the 1% and (no) Not Significant

b: Lag Length based on AIC

ARDL Bound test cointegration results

The ARDL bounds cointegration test, as shown in Table 4, presented an F-statistic value of 10.7213, which exceeds the upper critical bounds at the 1%, 2.5%, 5%, and 10% significance levels. This result leads to rejecting the null hypothesis, which states no long-run relationship (no cointegration) among the variables. Consequently, the findings suggest a long-term cointegrating relationship between the indicators included in the model.

Table 4. ARDL Bound test cointegration

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels of relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Significance	I (0)	I (1)
F-statistic	10.7213	10%	2.08	3
K	5	5%	2.39	3.38
		2.50%	2.7	3.73
		1%	3.06	4.15

The optimal lag structure for the model was determined using the AIC selection criterion, resulting in the ARDL (2, 2, 2, 0, 2, 2) specification.

Results of ARDL long- and short-run

Table 5 shows the assessed long-run and short-run coefficients from the ARDL model and diagnostic test statistics. The estimated long-run coefficients showed that (LNRNE) had a positive but statistically insignificant relationship with CO₂ emissions. Population (LNPOP) and manufacturing value-added (LNMVA) exhibited negative but statistically insignificant relationships with CO₂ emissions. Furthermore, a positive but statistically insignificant correspondence between GDP (LNGDP) and CO₂ emissions suggested that long-term economic growth may lead to increased emissions. On the other hand, exports (LNEXP) had a negative but statistically insignificant relationship with CO₂ emissions in the long run. The computed short-run coefficients revealed that renewable energy consumption (LNRNE) had a statistically significant negative relationship with CO₂ emissions in both the current and lagged periods. In the current period, the population (LNPOP) had an undesirable but statistically irrelevant connection with CO₂ emissions, while in the lagged period, there was a positive and significant relationship. GDP

(LNGDP) exhibited an affirmative and statistically noteworthy link with CO₂ emissions in the current age but a negative and statistically significant relationship in the lagged period. Similarly, exports (LNEXP) had an adverse and statistically momentous relationship with CO₂ emissions in both the current and lagged periods. The error correction term (CointEq(-1)) was notably negative and statistically significant, indicating a long-run equilibrium connection and confirming cointegration among the variables. Regarding the diagnostic tests reported in Table 5, the chi-square (χ^2) normality test for residuals had a p-value of 0.3845, suggesting that the residuals are normally distributed. The chi-square (χ^2) LM serial correlation test had a p-value of 0.621, indicating no serial correlation in the residuals. Additionally, the chi-square (χ^2) ARCH test for autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity had a p-value of 0.681, suggesting no presence of heteroscedasticity in the residuals. Finally, the chi-square (χ^2) Ramsey RESET test had a p-value of 0.8064, demonstrating that the model is correctly specified and no omitted variables exist. The diagnostic tests showed that the assessed ARDL model pleases the necessary assumptions and is correctly specified.

Table 5. ARDL estimated results

Long run	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	P-value
LNRNE	3.472795	4.345253	0.799216	0.4385
LNPOP	-1.245746	1.294881	-0.962055	0.3536
LNMAVA	-1.157789	0.945873	-1.224044	0.2427
LNGDP	4.559599	3.892059	1.171513	0.2624
LNEXP	-0.265634	0.361417	-0.73498	0.4754
Constant	-43.15943	42.30772	-1.020131	0.3263
Short run	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	P-value
D(LNCO2(-1))	-0.364417	0.096615	-3.771857	0.0023
D(LNRNE)	-1.890251	0.26109	-7.239843	0
D(LNRNE (-1))	-1.799475	0.344799	-5.218912	0.0002
D(LNPOP)	-0.110794	0.511063	-0.216791	0.8317
D(LNPOP (-1))	2.494586	0.58519	4.262862	0.0009
D(LNGDP)	1.674189	0.373707	4.479952	0.0006
D(LNGDP (-1))	-2.625651	0.469006	-5.598336	0.0001
D(LNEXP)	-0.413489	0.053699	-7.700112	0
D(LNEXP (-1))	-0.31992	0.059891	-5.341687	0.0001
CointEq (-1) *	-0.430921	0.041145	-10.47316	0
Diagnostic test				
χ^2 normality			0.621	0.3845
χ^2 ARCH			0.415825	0.681
χ^2 Serial			0.3586	0.621
χ^2 Reset			0.250129	0.8064

***p<1%, **p<5%; AIC (ARDL (2, 2, 2, 0, 2, 2))

Diagnostic tests

The stability and reliability of the model were tested using the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests. These tests help to evaluate if the model's structure remains consistent and stable over the entire study period. Fig 2(a) and 2(b) show the results of the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests, respectively.

In Fig 2(a), the CUSUM plot stays within the acceptable range of $\pm 5\%$ throughout the study. This means the model's coefficients or parameters remain stable and do not change significantly over the sample period. Similarly, Fig 2(b) showed that the CUSUMSQ estimates also stay within the critical limits of $\pm 5\%$ during the entire investigation. This suggests no significant structural breaks or instability in the model's variance. The graphical representations of the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests denote that the model's parameters are structurally stable because the scatter plots do not deviate beyond the maximum allowed deviation of 5% from the critical bounds. This means that the model was reliable and consistent throughout the study period.

Figure 2(a). Cumulative sum of recursive residuals

Figure 2(b). Cumulative sum of squares of recursive residuals

Granger causality test results

The Granger causality test was accompanied by an analysis of whether changes in one variable (exports or CO₂ emissions) can help predict or explain future changes in the other variable. The test examines if there is a potential cause-and-effect relationship between the two variables. The null hypothesis for each test states that the first variable does not influence or cause changes in the second variable. The results showed no evidence that exports (LNEXP) and carbon emissions (LN CO₂) have a causal relationship in either direction. The null hypotheses could not be rejected at commonly used significance levels. Additionally, GDP (LNGDP) does not Granger-cause carbon emissions (LNCO₂), but the p-value of 0.069 suggests relatively weak evidence against the reverse causality from LNCO₂ to LNGDP. There is no Granger causality between manufacturing value-added (LNMVA), population (LNPOP), (LNRNE), and CO₂ emissions (LNCO₂) in either direction. The null hypothesis that exports (LNEXP) do not Granger-cause GDP (LNGDP) and vice versa cannot be rejected, indicating any Granger causality between these two variables. However, manufacturing value-added (LNMVA) Granger causes GDP (LNGDP) at the 1% significance level, but the reverse causality does not hold. Renewable energy consumption (LNRNE) Granger-causes GDP (LNGDP) at the 5% significance level, but GDP does not Granger-cause renewable energy consumption. The Granger causality test did not find any evidence that changes in manufacturing value-added (LNMVA), population (LNPOP), and renewable energy consumption (LNRNE) help predict or explain future changes in each other. There was no causal relationship among these variables in either direction. However, the test results suggest that changes in manufacturing value-added and renewable energy consumption can help predict or explain future changes in GDP in Ghana, but not vice versa. In other words, GDP does not have predictive power for manufacturing value-added and renewable energy consumption. Additionally, the test did not suggest a contributory connection between CO₂ emissions and the other variables, except for a relatively weak indication that changes in carbon emissions may help predict or explain future changes in GDP, but not the reverse.

Table 6. Granger causality test

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests			
Null Hypothesis:	F-Statistic	Prob.	Decision
LNEXP does not Granger Cause LNCO ₂	0.31698	0.7314	Not Rejected
LNCO ₂ does not Granger Cause LNEXP	0.30775	0.738	Not Rejected
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNCO ₂	2.99478	0.069	Not Rejected
LNCO ₂ does not Granger Cause LNGDP	0.7382	0.4885	Not Rejected
LNMVA does not Granger Cause LNCO ₂	0.46991	0.6307	Not Rejected
LNCO ₂ does not Granger Cause LNMVA	0.513	0.6051	Not Rejected
LNPOP does not Granger Cause LNCO ₂	1.20091	0.3184	Not Rejected
LNCO ₂ does not Granger Cause LNPOP	2.09088	0.1455	Not Rejected
LNRNE does not Granger Cause LNCO ₂	1.44047	0.2566	Not Rejected
LNCO ₂ does not Granger Cause LNRNE	0.63852	0.5368	Not Rejected
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNEXP	0.05263	0.9488	Not Rejected

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests			
Null Hypothesis:	F-Statistic	Prob.	Decision
LNEXP does not Granger Cause LNGDP	0.03219	0.9684	Not Rejected
LNMVA does not Granger Cause LNEXP	0.36645	0.697	Not Rejected
LNEXP does not Granger Cause LNMVA	0.65049	0.5307	Not Rejected
LNPOP does not Granger Cause LNEXP	0.36842	0.6957	Not Rejected
LNEXP does not Granger Cause LNPOP	1.66821	0.2097	Not Rejected
LNRNE does not Granger Cause LNEXP	0.83931	0.4443	Not Rejected
LNEXP does not Granger Cause LNRNE	2.17752	0.1352	Not Rejected
LNMVA does not Granger Cause LNGDP	6.2536	0.0065	Rejected
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNMVA	1.50214	0.2429	Not Rejected
LNPOP does not Granger Cause LNGDP	1.57217	0.2282	Not Rejected
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNPOP	2.11551	0.1425	Not Rejected
LNRNE does not Granger Cause LNGDP	5.46133	0.0111	Rejected
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNRNE	2.50382	0.1029	Not Rejected
LNPOP does not Granger Cause LNMVA	1.4415	0.2563	Not Rejected
LNMVA does not Granger Cause LNPOP	0.7708	0.4738	Not Rejected
LNRNE does not Granger Cause LNMVA	0.38907	0.6819	Not Rejected
LNMVA does not Granger Cause LNRNE	2.50945	0.1024	Not Rejected
LNRNE does not Granger Cause LNPOP	1.6456	0.2139	Not Rejected
LNPOP does not Granger Cause LNRNE	1.02956	0.3724	Not Rejected

The research discovered a long-term association among CO₂ emissions, RNE, population size, manufacturing output, gross domestic product, and exports. This conclusion is reliable, as are several other recent studies that used the ARDL cointegration approach to analyze similar variables. Some of these previous papers that align with the current findings include the works by Raihan and Tuspekova, published in 2022, and separate studies by Raihan, published in 2023. These earlier researches also identified a long-run cointegrating link among indicators such as CO₂ emissions, renewable energy use, population, manufacturing output, GDP, and exports. The study also found a positive long-run GDP-emissions relationship, which suggests that higher emissions are associated with economic growth. The finding of a long-run cointegrating link among CO₂ emissions, RNE, population, manufacturing output, GDP, and exports aligns with the observations made by Raihan and Tuspekova (2022b, 2022c) and Raihan (2023c, 2023d) in their respective studies. Destek and Sinha (2020) and Lin and Ullah (2023) also found a positive long-term link between GDP and CO₂ emissions in European Union states, although the short-term dynamics differed. The study observed a negative long-run relationship between POP and emissions, unfailing with the conclusions of Raihan and Tuspekova (2022c) and Raihan (2023d), but the short-run effects were mixed. This finding is further supported by Zafar et al. (2019), who reported a positive long-run association between population growth and carbon emissions in Asian countries. However, the insignificant negative relationship between MVA and emissions contrasts with Raihan and Tuspekova's (2022b) research, which found a positive link. Furthermore, Shahbaz et al. (2018) and Adedoyin et al. (2020) also found a positive long-run relationship between manufacturing output and CO₂ emissions in BRICS countries.

Regarding renewable energy consumption, the study found a positive but insignificant long-run relationship with emissions. This result contrasts with the studies by Zouhair and Boudghene Stambouli (2021), Oliveira and Moutinho (2021), and Cheng et al. (2019), who observed a harmful link. However, the negative short-run relationship matches the discoveries of Paramati et al. (2017). This result is further supported by Oliveira and Moutinho (2021), who observed a negative long-run link between RNE and CO₂ emissions in OECD states.

Conclusions and Discussions

Conclusions

The research used an empirical analysis to examine Ghana's ability to decouple economic development from CO₂ emissions, concentrating on the manufacturing, export, and adoption of renewable energy sectors. The study found a long-term cointegrating relationship among CO₂ emissions, RNE, POP, manufacturing output, GDP, and exports. Notably, over the same period, the export sector showed a negative but statistically insignificant relationship with CO₂ emissions, while GDP showed a positive but statistically insignificant relationship with CO₂ emissions. This indicates that sustained economic growth may lead to higher emissions. However, the research revealed that renewable energy's short-term and long-term effects on CO₂ emissions differed. In the short term, higher use of renewable energy sources showed a statistically significant and negative correlation with CO₂ emissions, suggesting that adopting renewable energy sources could quickly reduce emissions. Although the long-term correlation between CO₂ emissions and RNE was statistically insignificant, this finding implies that other factors or variables may limit or influence the long-term effect of adopting RNE on reducing emissions. Moreover, the research initiated that over time, population increase and the development of the manufacturing sector, as shown by manufacturing value-added, showed negative but statistically negligible correlations with CO₂ emissions. These results imply that even if population rise and industrial activity may not eventually directly lead to higher emissions, their possible effects on environmental deterioration should not be disregarded. The research did not provide thorough empirical support for Ghana's EKC theory. According to the EKC theory, ecological dilapidation intensifies with economic expansion and falls at a specific turning point or income level. This connection is inverted U-shaped. However, the research could not pinpoint a precise turning point during the studied period when economic development resulted in lower CO₂ emissions, suggesting that the EKC theory could not entirely fit Ghana's particular situation or might take longer to materialize. The outcomes of this paper stress Ghana's need to put into practice focused laws and plans meant to encourage RNE, ecological practices in the manufacturing and export sectors, and technological advancements to help the nation move toward a low-CO₂ economy. Ghana can reduce its CO₂ footprint, balance economic growth and environmental sustainability, support international initiatives to slow climate change, and accomplish sustainable development objectives by tackling five critical areas.

Policy implications

It is essential to create a thorough national renewable energy strategy and action plan in addition to financial incentives and infrastructural investments to hasten the use of RNE, such as solar, wind, and hydropower. Complementing this should be the promotion of green export goods, cleaner manufacturing technology, and strict environmental laws to promote sustainable practices in the export industry. The first necessary measures include establishing precise emission reduction goals and standards for the industrial sector, offering financial and technical support for energy-efficient technology, and endorsing the ideas of the circular economy. Family planning and reproductive health initiatives should also be stressed, even if funding energy-efficient infrastructure, public transit systems, and sustainable urban planning techniques will lessen the environmental effects of population increase and urbanization. Creating a robust monitoring and evaluation system to assess development, ongoing policy review and updating based on empirical data, and stakeholder cooperation is crucial. The exchange of information and technology may be facilitated by actively engaging in international projects, looking for bilateral and multilateral alliances, and encouraging regional cooperation and knowledge-sharing platforms. Ghana can use these chances to adopt efficient decoupling plans catered to its particular situation and learn from best practices in separating economic development from CO₂ emissions.

Study Limitations

The analysis is based on a relatively small sample size covering 1990 to 2020. Additionally, the use of aggregated national-level data might obscure significant regional or sector-specific variations within Ghana. Moreover, since the study relies on secondary data from the World Bank Indicator database, any shortcomings or inconsistencies in the original data collection process could affect the findings. Furthermore, because the study focused on a restricted set of variables, it may have overlooked other potentially critical factors that influence CO₂ emissions and economic growth.

Recommendations for Future Research

Future research could build on this study using broader variables, such as foreign direct investment, technological advancement indices, and more specific energy use data. Researchers may also consider employing other econometric techniques, such as nonlinear ARDL or panel data analysis, to capture correlations and cross-country comparisons. Future research could broaden the time window and employ higher frequency data if accessible.

Abbreviations (Nomenclature)

<i>GDP</i>	Economic Growth
<i>POP</i>	Population Growth
<i>MVA</i>	Manufacturing Value-Added
<i>EXP</i>	Export
<i>ARDL</i>	Autoregressive Distributed Lag

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